

PHYSICAL AND MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF FOAMED HDPE-BASED SYNTHETIC RATTAN

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1 Introduction

Rattan is a type of climbing palm that is very long with a slender stem which maintains an almost uniform diameter throughout its length. The outer portion of the stem is extremely hard and durable, while the inner portion of the stem is softer and porous. The straight rattan is usually steamed and then bent into the desired shape through the use of specialized shapers. Once the rattan has dried, it will retain its shape forever. These rattan poles are often used to form the frames of what will become rattan woven furniture such as chairs, tables and sofas. Rattan is a very good material mainly because it is lightweight, durable, and somewhat flexible. Nevertheless, natural rattan has been recently shortage and more expensive because rattan collection requires heavy labors and workers have to go deeper into jungles to collect them.

Since rattan furniture has been very popular in abroad due to its exotically tropical looks, its shortage in supply and difficulty to maintenance leads manufacturer to produce synthetic rattan made of plastics to replace natural ones. Most of them are prepared from high-density polyethylene (HDPE). Synthetic rattan offers good properties such as strength, toughness, flexibility, outdoor durability and elimination of risk to insect bite. Moreover, polyethylene-based rattan is waterproof, resistant to moulds, and weather-resistant. Unfortunately, synthetic rattan is usually heavier than natural rattan because of its dense structures (no porosity). Adding wood flour into HDPE to obtain wood-feel texture also reduces flexibility of synthetic rattan since incompatibility between these two materials.

This research aims to prepare light-weight synthetic rattan from composites between high-density polyethylene (HDPE), ethylene-propylene-diene elastomer (EPDM), and pine wood flour. A twin-screw extruder with a rod die was used to blend and

extrude composite strand. Wood flour content and silane coupling agent were varied. A chemical blowing agent with several contents was incorporated in order to produce fine foaming structure inside composite strands. Densities and mechanical properties of composite strands were examined. Color of specimen was measured using a color reader in Lab system. Morphology of fracture surface of the composite strands was studied by a scanning electron microscope.

2 Experimental

2.1 Materials

High-density polyethylene, HDPE (EL-LENETM H5480S, MFI = 0.8 g/10 min, 190°C/2.16 kg) was purchased from SCG Chemicals Co., Ltd. Thailand. Ethylene propylene diene monomer, EPDM (NORDELTM IP3720P) was purchased from Dow Chemical, USA. Pine wood flour (200 mesh size) was supplied by Linpai Co., China. Vinyltriethoxysilane (VTES) 97% from Sigma-Aldrich was used as coupling agent. Dicumyl peroxide (DCP) 98% from Aldrich Chemical Company was used as initiator. Chemical foaming agent (CFA) was azodicarbonamide (with ZnO) supplied by MDR international Co., Thailand. All resins and chemicals were used as received.

2.2 Fiber treatment

Prior treated with vinyltriethoxysilane (VTES), wood flour was dried in a vacuum oven at 80°C for 24 hrs to get rid of moisture. Eight liters of ethanol/water solution (95/5 wt%) was prepared and acetic acid was added to adjust pH to be 3.5. VTES 2.5 and 3 wt% (respect to the fiber weight) was added into ethanol/water solution with slow stirring for 30 min to generate active groups. Then, 400 g of dried wood flour was poured into VTES solution

and maintained stirring for 6 hrs. After that, silane-treated wood flour was dried in a vacuum oven at 120°C for 24 hrs. Treated wood flour was characterized by FTIR.

2.3 Compounding and fabrication

HDPE (90 wt%) and EPDM (10 wt%) were compounded in a twin-screw extruder (SHJ-25, China) with a temperature profile of 150-160°C at screw speed of 30 rpm and then pelletized. Prior mixing with polymer compounds, silane-treated wood flour was dried in vacuum oven at 80°C for 24 hrs in order to minimize amount of moisture. Polymer compounds, silane-treated wood (at 1, 2 and 3 phr) and DCP (0.5wt% with respect to the fiber weight) were melt blending in a twin-screw extruder with a temperature profile of 150-180°C at screw speed of 30 rpm and a rod die with diameter of 4 mm. Composite strands were cooled in a water bath with controlled water temperature of 40°C. Composite strands were tested their mechanical properties to determine the optimum formula for the next step.

The optimized formula was melt blended in the presence of modified azodicarbonamide (at 0.5, 1, 1.5 and 2 phr) by a twin-screw extruder with a temperature profile of 150-180°C at screw speed of 30 rpm and a rod die with diameter of 4 mm. Strands were cooled in a water bath with controlled water temperature of 40°C. Foamed composite strands were collected and tested.

2.4 Physical and mechanical testing

Prior to testing, composite strands were examined their diameters carefully to select only uniform specimen for physical and mechanical testing.

Mechanical properties of composite strands were carried out in a universal testing machine (Instron 5965, Series dual column table frames). Tensile test were performed according to ASTM-D2256 with a crosshead speed of 50 mm/min and 5 kN load cell, gauge length of 10 cm. Ten specimens were performed to determine the average and the standard deviation.

Color was measured by means of a color reader in Lab system. Density was performed according to ASTM D1622 using specimen length of 3 cm. Twenty specimen of each formula were measured in order to calculate the average and the standard deviation.

Cross-sections of natural and foamed synthetic strands were characterized by a scanning electron microscope (JSM-5410LV). Test specimens were prepared by immersing specimen in liquid nitrogen and then breaking them. The fractured surfaces were sputter-coated with gold for observation.

3 Results and discussion

3.1 Infrared spectroscopy analysis (FTIR)

FTIR analysis was used for studying the crosslinking reaction in the composites, i.e. the formation of wood–O–Si bonds and Si–O–Si bonds. Fig.1 shows the FTIR spectra of HDPE-based composites having untreated and VTES treated wood flour. In VTES treated samples, there was no peak at 1,092 cm^{-1} which was related to residual un-hydrolyzed Si–O–CH₃ groups [1]. The broad band between 900 and 1,150 cm^{-1} was related to either covalent bonding between wood and silane (Si–O–C) or polysiloxanes (Si–O–Si) bonding [1]. The peaks at 800 and 1050 cm^{-1} were attributed to polysiloxanes (Si–O–Si) confirming that there was silane crosslinking during the fiber treatment. Also, the peak at 1,650 cm^{-1} that could be assigned to C=C symmetric stretch from vinyl groups in VTES that would be used to react with HDPE in the compounding step.

3.2 Optimized wood content and silane treatment

Fig.2 (a) shows that HDPE-based composite strands had much lower Young's modulus compared to natural rattan but they offered better flexibility considered from percent of ultimate strains as presented in Fig.2 (b). Composite strands with VTES treated wood had higher Young's modulus and higher strain at ultimate stress than those with untreated wood. It can be seen that Young's modulus increased with respect to wood contents. From color measurement, it found that all composite strands were light brown but their lightness (L^*) was darker than natural rattan as presented in Fig. 2(c). Considering results of mechanical properties and color, the optimized wood content was 2 phr with silane treatment of 2.5 wt% of wood weight. SEM revealed good adhesion between wood fibers and polymer matrix after treated fibers with VTES silane. After foaming, it is found that mechanical properties such as tensile modulus and tensile strength did not affect much by porous cross-

sections. Ultimate strains of foamed composite strands were in the same range of non-foamed or

even better. This is due to EPDM phases which could improve ductility of HDPE [2].

Fig.1. FTIR spectra of untreated and VTES treated pine wood.

Fig.2. (a) Young's modulus (b) Strain at ultimate stress (%), (c) Lightness (L*); of natural rattan and composite strands synthetic rattan with varied pine wood contents and silane treated.

Fig.3. Densities of natural and foamed synthetic rattan with varied CFA contents.

Fig.4. Lightness (L*) of natural and foamed synthetic rattan with varied CFA contents.

Fig.5. Cross-sectional morphology of natural rattan (a), and foamed synthetic rattan with CFA of 0.5 (b), 1.0 (c), 1.5 (d), and 2.0 (e) phr.

3.3 Density of foamed synthetic rattan

Fig.3 shows that densities of foamed composite strands synthetic rattan had lower non-foamed ones due to adding CFA creates foam cells starting in the middle of the composite strands. Increasing contents of CFA up to 2 phr reduced strand densities due to higher content of CFA produced more foam cells [3]. Unfortunately, these densities were still higher than natural rattan. Creating foam cells inside composite strands lowered their densities up to 16%.

3.4 Color measurement

It is seen that creating foamed cells inside composite strands improved appearance of synthetic rattan. By naked eyes, their color looked closed to natural rattan. When measured in Lab system, L* of foamed composite strands was somewhat higher than non-foamed ones and were closed to natural rattan. The reason is more lights could pass through composite masses having small voids inside.

3.5 Morphology of foamed synthetic rattan

Fig.5 shows cross-sectional morphology of foamed composite strands compared with natural rattan. It is seen that natural rattan has porous structure from xylem (water ducts) in its longitudinal orientation. Adding CFA creates foam cells starting in the middle of the composite strands. Foam cells with low CFA contents (0.5, 1.0 phr) were all closed cells, and open foamed cells occurred when using higher CFA contents (1.5, 2.0 phr). Unstable pull-out of composite strands was happened if higher than 2.0 phr CFA was attempted because strand surface was exploded. Too cool water temperature was prohibited due to occurrence of central voids from excessive shrinkage of polymer matrix inside.

4. Conclusions

Based on Young's modulus, strains at ultimate stress and its color, the optimized wood content was 2 phr with silane treatment of 2.5 wt% of wood weight. Densities of foamed composite strands synthetic

rattan had lower non-foamed ones. L* in Lab system of foamed composite strands was somewhat higher than non-foamed ones and were closed to natural rattan. Adding CFA, foam cells with low CFA contents (0.5, 1.0 phr) were all closed cells, and open foamed cells occurred when using higher CFA contents (1.5, 2.0 phr).

5. References

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